

IS ENES3 Data Request Review May 2020 - Report

20th May, 4pm UK

To join by zoom: <https://ukri.zoom.us/j/98298425463>

Agenda

- Sections below describe requirements and initial plans
- Topics for discussion
 - Objectives of meeting and this group
 - Mich: timely meeting .. while CMIP6 is full swing. CMIP6 is going a significant step further than prev. CMIP. WCRP is in an interesting phase, new strategy, developing new implementations. JSC just closed the opening meeting; reports in coming months. Strong emphasis on bringing modeling and data elements closer. At the early stage of developing CMIP7 ... call to establish CMIP project office ... to equip CMIP with a coordination function (administration and logistic support).
 - Paul: [obs4MIPs](#) -- expands on the observational side, with [input4MIPs](#) doing a similar thing. They both depend on the CF Process. They both aim to bring observations toward the standards defined by CMIP
 - Mich: that applies to reanalyses as well (ana4MIPs and CREATE-IP)...
 - -- within obs4MIPs, CMOR is being used, building the CMOR tables files downstream from the CMIP6 request ... tweaked for observations. Many observational quantities are not directly comparable with model output. But having these tables from this large archive of variables is a great resource.
 - Klaus: underscore utilities ... in ESMval .. it is great to see obs4MIPs in this standard format which facilitates automated data use.
 - Karl: a lot of overlap with obs4mips and inputs4mips, but the challenge of the data request is getting information in from MIPs. Very different when observational groups have a unique focus on specific variables.
 - Alison: need better integration with CF standard names process. MIPs did not know about the CF process (including knowing who Alison is).
 - Klaus: spreadsheets have problems ...
 - Karl:
 - Paul: spreadsheet a great format for starting to coalesce information across teams, but not great for finalising. An alternative, and a way to reduce the manual interactions, would be to use a web form for each entry, this would also allow checks to be made real-time catching inconsistencies before they are submitted for review. Good for initial iteration. But finalisation is difficult. Propose: is there a better way.
 - Review requirements
 - Review plans

Meet again in one month;

Karl: encourage people to add views on links. This document is a useful roadmap.

Martin: I will send a doodle and set up a meeting in June. Split this document to keep roadmap separate and re-usable.

Requirements

High Level Requirements

- Avoid disruptive changes: continued support for existing APIs for CMIP6 and smooth transition to CMIP7;
- Clear up linkages with ES-DOC and CMIPX CVs;
- Database Normalisation: linkage between tables should be SQL compatible (one attribute targets at most one table);
- Structural Rationalisation:
 - use same semantics for linking and grouping in experiments and variables, so clients can use simpler and clearer logic;
 - Clarify approach to groups, collections etc.
- Clarify External Dependencies: some parts of the request need broad consultation with the scientific community (mainly descriptive content), others need to be checked for compatibility with other services (especially CMOR, also other groups [IPSL XIOS](#) already integral in NEMO and being integrated in EC-Earth4 atmosphere; GFDL working on similar activity; Need to understand dependencies of other software tools).
- Strip out excessive complexity -- e.g. data volume estimation -- which can be handled by downstream software.
- Clarify definitions of attributes and external dependencies: hundreds of attributes used .. some have unclear meaning through lack of clarity in their purpose .. others have unclear documentation.

CMIP7 Forward Look in Github

https://github.com/cmip6dr/cmip7_forward_look

Issues raised during the CMIP6 process which could not be resolved (for lack of time, or because any reasonable solution would be too disruptive). There are 56 issues, many related to CF Conventions implementation decisions and other aspects of content. The following 10 items relate to the schema:

- Multiple experiment start dates [\[#56\]](#)
- Clarify approach on ancillary variables [\[#53\]](#)

- variable names for latitude and longitude of ocean variables are not standard -- would be easier if they were standardised. Users should use the meta-data, but scientists want to rely on variable names.
 - Behaviour of CMOR is sometimes taken to be part of the standard
 - Many of the issues Klaus Z noted with ocean grid variables/coordinates are due to data being written without using CMOR (even though a `cmor_version` is identified in the file written, e.g. CMIP5 files).
- Clarify rules on file names to avoid clashes [#50] and approach to requests with partial overlaps. See also #1
 - Defining methods attached to some classes [#45]
 - Separating what is wanted (e.g. percentage area covered) from implementation (e.g. [#33])
 - Objectives: experiment objectives vs. data selection objectives [#31]
 - Dealing with options in cell methods strings (e.g. [#27])
 - Specifying the time of day required which sub-daily data is requested [#21]
 - Changing the vocabulary used for variable types from FORTRAN [#18]
 - Specify intervals for calculations of time mean [#9]

ACTION: Martin: Arrange a follow-up meeting. In Progress:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1wylSpCAzd3C5jFccpd0HGIEoQJsKAdnLW69hF5fg0EU/edit?usp=sharing>

ACTION: Martin: Create a roadmap document. Done:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/15ikAVVOCGXFZqLNQ-xsW2673SAnbUJUDwwwF_ZUhB1U/edit?usp=sharing